

INTRODUCTION TO TEACHING WITH CANVAS

IN PARTNERSHIP WITH THE ONLINE EDUCATION INSTITUTE

SELF-PACED

canvas

Hello and welcome to Introduction to Teaching with Canvas (the Self-Paced version). This course introduces Canvas tools in the context of practical strategies for design, development, and management of an online course. You will have an opportunity to review the basics of online course development and practice the use of Canvas tools through hands-on exercises. This is a self-paced version of our four week facilitated course. Based on the original design, the course is presented in four modules (learning units) that contain all of the content for the topic. You will be able to navigate through the modules freely; however, we recommend you proceed through the content linearly as presented for the most beneficial learning journey.

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Course Description

This course introduces you to how to teach using the Canvas learning management system by Instructure. You will learn how the system works through a series of curated readings and recall what you have learned through formative quizzes. You will also be provided with an opportunity to practice what you have learned through a series of hands-on exercises focused on the subject you teach.

Learning Outcomes

By the end of the course, you will be able to use Canvas to apply Chickering and Gamson's "Seven Principles of Effective Teaching" in the following ways:

- Facilitate contact between students and faculty by creating a bio and setting communication expectations
- Develop reciprocity and cooperation among students by creating a community of discourse on discussions
- Encourage active learning by choosing a course home page that will help students succeed
- Give prompt feedback through the use of immediately scored exams
- Emphasize time on task by adding events to the course calendar
- Communicate high expectations by sharing the syllabus online
- Respect diverse talents and ways of learning by presenting content in a variety of formats

Self-Paced Communication Policy

As this is a non-facilitated self-paced course, there is no instructor to communicate with. We recommend creating a Canvas Community account, and joining the California Community College group so you have a place to ask questions and gain additional information and insight about using Canvas.

Canvas Community: <https://community.canvaslms.com/welcome>

California Community College Group*: <https://community.canvaslms.com/groups/ccc>

**Please note, this is a private group; you must request to join the group.*

Time Commitment & Recommended Skills

Your time commitment will vary based upon your own level of experience with web technologies. As this is a self-paced course, you may spend as much (or as little) time as you need reviewing the instructional content and practicing the skills presented.

Although this class is designed for novice Canvas users you should have the following:

- Basic computer skills (word processing, e-mail, file management)
- Basic internet skills (use of browser, searches, uploading/downloading files)
- Familiarity with discussion boards
- An open mind and willingness to try new things

Technical Requirements

- Fairly recent Mac or PC (not more than three years old) with a current operating system.
- Current browser (Firefox or Chrome are preferable)
- Internet connection, preferably broadband -- for viewing online videos

User Account on the Canvas Server

We recommend that you practice the hands-on activities presented throughout this class using a sandbox on the Instructure Canvas server.

There are some benefits to creating your Sandbox on the Instructure Canvas server, for example, you'll always have a place where you can test items, features, and apps, even if they are not installed at your local campus; and if you teach at more than one campus, this sandbox will provide you a college free repository to store all your course content that will always be available, even if you move schools or no longer teach a specific course. There are additional benefits, but ultimately the choice of where you practice is up to you.

If you decide to create a free sandbox account on the Instructure Canvas server, you will need to create a free user account. You can do this by going to <http://canvas.instructure.com> and clicking on the "Need a Canvas Account?" link, then follow the onscreen prompts to create a Teacher account (and don't forget to use an email address with a .edu domain). OR, you can watch this [video demonstration](#) for more information on creating your sandbox account.

Textbook Info

There is no required textbook to purchase for this class. All readings will be available online in Canvas. Many of them will be in the online Canvas guides, and you will be able to bookmark or print them for future reference.

Strongly Recommended Tools

You will be exposed to many, many websites and resources in this class. You may wish to take time to develop a process for bookmarking these sites for future reference.

If you don't have a clear bookmarking process or tool in mind, set up a free account at a social bookmarking site, like [Diigo](#). Diigo is an easy way to tag and bookmark websites, providing you with the ability to access them from any computer with an internet connection and share them with others.

Or you can use a digital workspace like [Evernote](#). Evernote is a workspace that lives across your phone, tablet, and computer, where you can create notes, collect info, find what you need, and present your ideas to the world.